

DISCONTINUITIES IN THE ADSORPTION OF POLYBASIC ACIDS FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS ON ALUMINA GEL

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Further studies of the adsorption of polybasic acids (oxalic, succinic, tartaric, citric) by alumina gel under similar conditions show that the adsorption of monobasic acids on alumina gel is continuous, while that of polybasic acids is discontinuous and irregular, exhibiting maximum and minimum points at different equilibrium concentrations.

Dewey (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 3187) studied the adsorption of oxalic and acetic acids on alumina gel and found no compound formation in either case, and observed that oxalic acid was adsorbed very strongly at low concentrations. The adsorption isotherms drawn by him are continuous, provided that a considerable number of points are left without joining, otherwise it is quite irregular. Sen (*ibid.*, 1927, 31, 680) found freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide to develop a very high adsorptive power for acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and Activation of Alumina Gel.—Aluminium hydroxide was obtained as a flocculent gelatinous precipitate by slow addition of ammonium hydroxide under vigorous stirring to a solution of aluminium sulphate at 24°. Yoe (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2390) found that a higher temperature of precipitation was detrimental to the adsorptive power of the gel. This was washed free of all impurities. The process of filtration and purification appeared difficult and took about 25 days. It has now been obtained in a hard, glass-like form by slow-drying in an air-oven at 60-70°. As regards the suitable temperature of roasting, there is, however, no unanimity. Perry (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1462) used a temperature of 200°; Munro and Johnson (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 88) activated alumina gel at 400°; Wood *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1926, 18, 169) activated it at 1000°, and Dunstan and others (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 179T) recommended 600°-700° for bauxite. We activated alumina gel at 280°-290° according to Chowdhury and Bagchi (*this Journal*, 1928, 8, 111) for about 4 hours. The water content of the gel on ignition was found to be 14.32%.

Analysis.—The adsorption experiments were carried out by weighing exactly 0.5 g. of the gel in clear, dry, glass bottles, similar in size, to which 100 c.c. portions of the acid solutions of varying concentrations in freshly prepared distilled water were pipetted. The bottles were stoppered and shaken for the same length of time (30 minutes) and kept for about 18 hours at the room temperature usually around 19°, at the end of which interval the equilibrium concentration of the solute (C_1) was determined in the supernatant liquid by the usual analytical method, using caustic soda and phenolphthalein as indicator. The original concentration (C_0) of the solute was determined under the same conditions from the blank experiment (without gel). The amount of

adsorption (x) was determined by difference ($C_0 - C_e$) for 100 c.c. of the aqueous solutions; x/m , the amount of adsorption per g. of alumina gel, was then calculated. Equilibrium concentration was calculated in millimoles per litre. The experiments were repeated with every care. The points in many cases were taken very close together and the estimation of the acids at these points was followed by a special method (Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations", 1926, p. 148) as described below.

At the end of the burette a jet of fine bore was attached by a small piece of rubber tubing to reduce the volume of one drop. The volume of one drop was found out by counting the number of droplets in a certain known volume of liquid (water). The average of a number of experiments was taken, and the volume of one drop was found to be 0.025 c.c., i.e., 4 drops were equal to 0.1 c. c.

In the previous work (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 685; 1941, 18, 321, 585; 1953, 30, 772) on adsorption of polybasic acids, bi-salts and hydroxybenzenes by activated sugar charcoal and silica gel, the adsorption was found to be highly influenced by the basicity of the acids. Results obtained by the present study confirm the previous observation (*loc. cit.*). It is found that the adsorption isotherm in the case of mono-basic acids is invariably a straight line, while in the case of polybasic acids, zigzag curves (Fig. 1) are obtained which appear to be periodic. Dewey (*loc. cit.*) would have arrived at similar zigzag curves for oxalic acid on alumina gel if he had joined all the points.

FIG. 1

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to oxalic, citric, tartaric and succinic acid.

In each case, the differences between the equilibrium molar concentrations at the maxima and minima points are multiple with few exceptions. This may be due to the fact that they might be displaced from their right places.

Electrometric study of the rate of adsorption of acids by sugar charcoal (*loc. cit.*) suggested the complexity occurring on the surface of the adsorbent. It is also found that the curves are not reproducible in detail, indicating the adsorbent surfaces of different activity. Further work is in progress to find out some explanation for these irregularities.

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